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Research Article

RISK ASSESSMENT AND PREVALENCE OF HOSPITAL- ACQUIRED INFECTIONS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Background & objectives: A major challenge to patient safety that has serious public health implications by changing the quality of life of patients and sometimes causing disability or even death is Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs). The true research and number remains unknown in developing countries.

To estimate point prevalence of HAI and study the associated risk factors in a tertiary care hospital are the objectives of this study.

Methods: A series of cross-sectional surveys were conducted between March and August in 2017. A structured data entry form was used to acquire patient data when they were admitted to the hospital. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention guidelines were used to identify and diagnose patients with HAI.

Results: Overall prevalence found of HAI was 3.76 per cent which included medical ICU (20%), Surgical Intensive Care Unit (ICU) (25%), ward (20%) and paediatric ward (12.17%) were identified to have significant association with HAI. Major reasons of acquiring HAI were found to be, prolonged hospital stay, mechanical ventilation, use of urinary catheter and exposure to central air-conditioning had higher odds of HAI ($P < 0.05$).

Interpretation & conclusions: A progressive reduction was shown by HAI prevalence over successive rounds of survey. There is a strong need of a conscious effort to be undertaken by all concerned to reduce hospital stay duration. Use of medical devices should be minimized and used judiciously. A priority of every healthcare provider should be healthcare infection control. Serious efforts and surveys should be undertaken in a planned and efficient manner to reduce HAI in healthcare facilities.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), also known as healthcare-associated infections (HCAI), are infections occurring in a patient in a hospital or other healthcare facility in whom the infection was not present or incubating at the time of admission¹. Healthcare Acquired Infections are a major challenge to patient safety and has a high impact in terms of morbidity and mortality^{2,3}.

Effective management and knowledge of HAIs helps in identification, intervention and documenting the effectiveness of that intervention and thus directing future infection control practices also in improving the quality of healthcare. The risk of acquiring HAI is possible everywhere and pervades every system worldwide with some countries having a national surveillance system for HAIs. However, the true burden remains unknown in many nations, particularly in developing countries⁴. Limited data is available regarding this issue in Pakistan. Point prevalence survey of HAIs and use of indwelling devices and antimicrobials in a large tertiary care hospital reported overall prevalence of HAIs as high as 7%. A study carried out in India in a burn unit reports that the infection density being 36.2 infections per 1000 patient-days⁶. The present study included all wards from paediatric to medicine at Holy family hospital Rawalpindi. Identifying the common risk factors associated with HAI was one of the objectives of this study.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

The study comprised a series of four rounds of point prevalence surveys carried out during March to August 2017. All hospital wards were included in this survey.

Data collection:

The data collection in the study was done keeping in mind the supportive literature search on various factors associated with HAIs. Suggestions of the concerned experts of various departments including Medicine, Community Medicine and statisticians of the institute was taken. The comprehensive data

collection questionnaire included patient's demographic data, patient's diagnosis, ward-wise location, consultant speciality, use of medical devices and mechanical ventilation, surgical procedures, antimicrobials and additional HAI risk factors were included in the details. Rigorous survey was undertaken ranging from paediatric to all general and speciality wards on the male and female side.

Definition of hospital-acquired infections (HAIs):

HAI patients were detected on the basis of HAI definition as per the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) guidelines⁷. HAIs, also called 'nosocomial infections', are infections acquired during hospital care, which are not present, or incubating at the time of admission. Infections that occur 48 hours after admission were considered nosocomial infections or HAIs.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

All patients were included in the study who were admitted for more than 48 h in the hospital. Blood, pus, urine, tracheal aspirate, sputum, bronchoalveolar lavage and stool, as appropriate, were collected from HAI suspects for microbiological testing. The standard protocols were followed in the collection of samples. The antibacterial susceptibility testing was performed by Vitek 2 Compact (Biomerieux, France) automated system for the identification and antimicrobial susceptibility testing of microorganisms.

Statistical analysis:

The questionnaire of the point prevalence survey was thoroughly scrutinized to ensure consistency of data in all the rounds. Statistical analysis was carried out using statistical software SPSS version 22.0 (IBM, USA) and Epi Info (CDC, Atlanta). Univariate analyses of the association between HAIs and the risk factors were performed using odds ratios (ORs). Maximum likelihood estimates of OR together with 95 per cent confidence intervals (CIs) were computed. Multivariate analysis was done by logistic regression.

Table I.

POINT PREVALENCE OF HAI			827
Characteristics	Not infected (n=1815)	Infected (n=71)	All (n=1886)
Device use, n (%)			
Urinary catheter	154 (8.48)	30(42.30)	184 (9.80)
Bladder instrumentation	8 (0.44)	1(1.40)	9 (0.50)
Peripheral iv catheter	620(34.16)	55(77.50)	675(35.80)
Central iv catheter	59(3.25)	13(18.30)	72(3.80)
Mechanical ventilation	28(1.50)	16(22.50)	44(2.30)
Drains and tubes	111 (6.12)	24(33.80)	135 (7.20)
Total	980 (54)	139 (196)	1119 (59)
Settings surgery performed, n (%)			
Elective open	391(83.91)	26(70.27)	417(82.90)
Emergency open	48 (10.30)	10(27.03)	58 (11.53)
Elective laparoscopy	24(5.15)	1(2.70)	25(4.97)
Emergency laparoscopic	3 (0.64)	0	3 (0.60)
Total	466 (100)	37 (100)	503 (100)
Degree of contamination, n (%)			
Clean	325(69.74)	13(35.14)	338(67.20)
Clean-contaminated	96 (20.60)	13(35.14)	109(21.67)
Contaminated	25(5.36)	6 (16.22)	31(6.16)
Dirty	20(4.29)	5 (13.51)	25(4.97)
Total	466 (100)	37 (100)	503 (100)

Table II. Prevalence of hospital-acquired infections according to patient characteristics (including risk factors) and specialties

Characteristics	Prevalence of HAI (%)	Unadjusted		Adjusted	
		OR (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	OR (95% CI)	<i>P</i>
Sex					
Male	3.5	1 (0.43-1.30)	0.23	1.00 (reference)	
Female	4.65	0.74		1.28 (0.62-2.66)	0.495
Age (yr)					
Neonates	4.54	1.00 (0.06-17.02)	0.18	0.13 (0.005-3.46)	0.22
Infants	15.62	3.44 (0.38-31.48)		0.41 (0.05-3.43)	0.41
1-13	7.40	1.63 (0.19-14.26)		0.34 (0.04-2.56)	0.30
14-19	16.27	3.58 (0.41-30.97)		3.37 (0.90-12.63)	0.07
20-29	2.46	0.54 (0.07-4.44)		0.93 (0.35-2.44)	0.88
30-39	1.90	0.42 (0.05-3.45)		0.62 (0.23-1.62)	0.33
40-49	1.88	0.42 (0.05-3.71)		0.62 (0.19-1.99)	0.42
50-59	5.34	1.18 (0.15-9.42)		1.16 (0.46-2.87)	0.74
≥60	5.97	1.31 (0.17-10.43)		1.00 (reference)	
Consultant speciality					
Paediatrics	12.17	4.17 (2.14-8.01)	0.001	8.77 (0.94-81.59)	0.056
Medicine and allied	2.57	0.52 (0.30-0.88)	0.009	0.95 (0.38-2.39)	0.922
Obstetrics and gynaecology	3.06	0.80 (0.20-2.69)	0.710	0.82 (0.15-4.31)	0.814
Orthopaedics	0	0.00	-	0.00	0.998
Dental	0	0.00	-	0.00	0.999
Surgery and allied	4.23	1.23 (0.74-2.04)	0.390	1.00 (reference)	
Ventilation					
Central AC	22.72	8.59 (3.78-19.10)	0.001	3.14 (0.96-10.27)	0.058
Split AC	11.43	4.20 (2.35-7.44)	0.001	1.41 (0.41-4.87)	0.581
Air cooler	0.82	0.19 (0.03-0.79)	0.009	0.79 (0.17-3.70)	0.772
Windows AC	0	0.00	-	0.00	-
Windows and fans	3.7	0.41 (0.25-0.68)	0.001	1.00 (reference)	
Hospital stay (days)					
<3	3.4	1	0.001	1.54 (0.17-13.84)	0.699
3-7	1.5	0.43		0.68 (0.26-1.76)	0.436
15-21	4.6	1.36		1.78 (0.72-4.43)	0.209
22-30	7.3	2.22		2.96 (1.10-7.97)	0.031
>30	9.1	2.81		2.31 (0.96-5.54)	0.061
8-14	2.5	0.71		1.00 (reference)	
Device use					
Mechanical ventilation	36.4	18.57 (9.01-38.07)	0.001	2.18 (0.75-6.27)	0.148
Urinary catheter	16.3	7.89 (4.65-13.37)	0.001	2.69 (1.22-5.95)	0.014
Drains and tubes	17.8	7.84 (4.47-13.69)	0.001	2.03 (0.93-4.44)	0.073
Central iv catheter	18.1	6.67 (3.28-13.36)	0.001	1.05 (0.04-2.76)	0.909

Peripheral iv catheter	8.1	6.63 (3.66-12.15)	0.001	2.42 (1.16-5.05)	0.018
Bladder instrumentation	11.1	3.23 (0.46-19.18)	0.240	0.46 (0.02-9.53)	0.620
Settings surgery performed					
Elective open	7.24	0.49(0.22-1.12)	0.06	1.63 (0.14-18.04)	0.687
Elective laparoscopy	4.55	0.56(0.03-4.08)	0.56	1.01 (0.10-9.67)	0.988
Emergency laparoscopic	0	0.00	-	0.00	-
Emergency open	22.22	3.44(1.45-8.02)	0.001	1.00 (reference)	
Degree of contamination					
Contaminated	25.00	3.56 (1.20-10.06)	0.006	0.62 (0.12-3.12)	0.565
Clean-contaminated	14.61	2.25(1.04-4.83)	0.020	0.27 (0.05-1.32)	0.106
Clean	4.36	0.26(0.12-0.54)	0.001	0.09 (0.02-0.41)	0.002
Dirty	27.78	12.55(3.81-38.93)	0.001	1.00 (reference)	
Additional risk factors					
Depressed consciousness (GCS <15) and prolonged use of neuromuscular agents or sedatives ⁸	62.5	18.43(7.43-45.20)	0.001	1.61 (0.44-5.82)	0.467
Transport from the ICU for diagnostic or therapeutic procedures	50	13.87(4.48-41.39)	0.001	4.20 (0.84-20.92)	0.080
Previous antibiotic exposure, particularly to third-generation cephalosporins within one month	23.07	6.35 (2.26-16.94)	0.001	1.80 (0.52-6.20)	0.350
Compromised immune status	15.38	4.31(1.81-9.90)	0.001	2.43 (0.97-6.07)	0.057
Renal failure, acute as per AKIN criteria ⁹	13.23	3.73(1.65-8.16)	0.001	2.97 (1.08-8.17)	0.035
and CKD as per KDOQI guidelines ¹⁰					
Cytotoxic chemotherapy	8.75	2.49(1.24-4.92)	0.001	4.35 (1.70-11.16)	0.002
Diabetes mellitus as per ADA criteria ¹¹	6.87	1.87(0.85-3.99)	0.080	-	-
H2 blocker, PPI or antacid therapy >48 h	5.76	1.57(0.79-3.07)	0.160	-	-
Malnutrition: BMI <18.5 kg/m ²	5.26	1.38(0.53-3.39)	0.460	-	-
Malignant tumours	4.95	1.35(0.74-2.43)	0.280		

RESULTS:

As per our inclusion criteria of the study 1886 patients in total spent 40,610 patient-days in the hospital, were included in the study, of whom 77.3% male and 22.7% females with a ratio of 1:0.29. 35 years was the median age (interquartile range 26-51 yo).

Table I shows the baseline data of the study population with respect to age, sex and admitting consultant speciality.

The survey was carried out as four rounds between March and August 2017. Seventy one cases of HAI were detected. Overall prevalence of HAI was 3.76

per cent (95% CI=2.97, 4.69). Prevalence of HAI cases detected was 5.6 per cent in the first round and went down to 4.9 per cent in the second round, 2.6 per cent in the third round and 1.6 per cent in the fourth round.

Overall rate of HAI was found to be 1.75 HAI cases per 1000 patient-days. It was 2.49 HAI cases per 1000 patient-days for the first round, 2.12 for the second round, 1.22 for the third round and 0.90 HAI cases per 1000 patient-days for the fourth round.

Surgical-site infections (SSIs) were identified to be the most common HAI (23.94%), followed by

hospital-acquired pneumonia (HAP) (18.31%), urinary tract infection (UTI) (16.9%), catheter-related bloodstream infection (BSI) (16.9%), ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) (9.85%), septicemia (8.45%) and others (5.65%).

Among consultant specialities, paediatric had the maximum odds of more than four times as compared to other specialities. The prevalence of HAI was highest in surgical Intensive Care Unit (ICU) ward (25%), followed by medical ICU (20%) and burns ward (20%). With regard to air-conditioning (AC) and ventilation in the wards, highest prevalence of HAI was seen in wards with central AC (22.72%), followed by split AC (11.43%). There is 8.59 times more chance of acquiring an HAI when a patient is exposed to central AC than other modalities of AC. Similarly, the odds were 4.20 times more when exposed to split AC (Table II) 8-11. The association between AC and HAI was found significant ($P < 0.05$) for all the modalities of ventilation.

HAI prevalence was seen to rise with the increase in duration of hospital stay. The odds of acquiring an HAI were 3.11, 3.85 and 5.24 times more when the duration of hospital stay exceeded 15, 22-30 or more than 30 days respectively.

Peripheral intravenous (iv) line was the most commonly used device, but the highest HAI prevalence (36.4%) was found amongst patients on mechanical ventilation, followed by central iv line (18.1%). The odds of acquiring an HAI were highest (18.57 times more) when a patient is exposed to mechanical ventilation. Similarly, the odds are 7.89, 7.84, 6.67 and 6.63 times more when exposed to urinary catheter, drains and tubes, central iv catheter and peripheral iv catheter, respectively (Table II).

Of the 16 HAI patients on mechanical ventilation, seven (43.75%) had VAP. Similarly, in 30 HAI patients with urinary catheters, nine (30%) had UTI. In 13 HAI patients with central iv catheter, three (23.07%) had BSI in addition to other types of HAIs. Depending on the setting of surgery (elective/emergency and open/laparoscopic), HAI prevalence was highest (22.22%) in emergency open setting. The odds of acquiring an HAI are 3.44 times more when a patient is operated under the emergency open setting. Most of the surgeries were performed under sterile or 'clean' conditions, while HAI prevalence (20%) was highest in the contaminated setting or 'dirty' category making the odds of getting an infection 3.48 times more 12.

The chance of acquiring an HAI was 18.43 for a

patient who had depressed consciousness (Glasgow Coma Score < 15)¹³ and was on prolonged use of neuromuscular agents or sedatives. Similarly, the odds were 13.87 for a patient transported from ICU for diagnostic or therapeutic procedures; 6.35 for previous antibiotic exposure (particularly to third-generation cephalosporin within one month), 4.31 for compromised immune status, 3.73 for renal failure and 2.49 for cytotoxic chemotherapy. These results were found significant ($P < 0.05$). Table II represents the OR along with 95 per cent CI and significance for various risk factors.

Logistic regression revealed that the association between HAI and use of urinary catheter and peripheral catheter was significant with increased odds of 2.69 and 2.42, respectively. Similarly, additional risk factors such as renal failure and cytotoxic chemotherapy were significantly associated with HAI, with increased odds of 2.97 and 4.35, respectively. Hospital stay of 22-30 days was significantly associated with HAI (OR=2.96), and surgeries performed under clean degree of contamination were found to be protective against HAI (OR=0.09).

DISCUSSION:

Most studies related to HAI conducted in developed countries demonstrate the efficacy of surveillance and its significant contribution to minimizing patient morbidity and mortality¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Conversely, in developing countries, only a few studies providing HAI using such standardized definitions are available. This study was that it included all age groups including paediatrics, regarding which very few reports are available in Pakistan that in itself is a benchmark 5.

The present study has found point prevalence of HAI to be 3.76 per cent (95% CI=2.97, 4.69), which was lower than the rates reported by other hospitals in many developing^{5,6} and developed countries¹⁸ as well. A systematic review has estimated hospital-wide prevalence of HAIs in high-income countries at 7.6 per cent and in low- and middle-income countries at 10.1 per cent⁴.

The European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) reports a mean HCAI prevalence of 7.1% in Europe¹⁸, and public health reports from the USA estimate it to be 4.5 per cent in 2002¹⁹. The English National Point Prevalence Survey on HCAI revealed that prevalence had reduced from 8.2 in 2006 to 6.4 per cent in 2011²⁰. Prospective surveillance of 12 ICUs of seven hospital members of the International Nosocomial Infection Control

Consortium of seven cities introduced from July 2004 to March 2007 reported an overall HCAI rate of 4.4 per cent and 9.06 HCAIs per 1000 ICU-days²¹.

Paediatrics had the highest odds of having HAI (>4 times) as compared to other specialities. A study from developing countries has reported that rates of neonatal infections were 3-20 times higher than those reported for hospital-born babies in industrialized countries²².

Our study showed that prevalence of HAI was highest in surgical ICU (25%), followed by medical ICU (20%) and burns ward (20%). Many studies found that the HAI burden was much more severe in patients admitted to ICUs, burn, transplant patients and neonates and might even go as high as 51 per cent^{23,24}.

Our study results corroborated with another study which showed that the duration of hospital stay was significantly associated with higher HAI prevalence, suggesting that conscious efforts need to be taken by all concerned to reduce the duration of hospitalization stay, to the minimum²⁵. High prevalence of HAI amongst patients on mechanical ventilation, central iv line and urinary catheter found in our study was similar to other studies²⁶⁻²⁸. In our study, SSI and HAP were the most common HAI types reported, which was similar to that reported in a systematic review and meta-analysis of HAI in developing countries³. As per other studies, the frequency of SSI varies between 1.2 and 5.2 per cent in high-income countries^{10,19,29}. VAP was also reported by other authors with an alarming rate³⁰⁻³¹. Our findings with regard to additional risk factors corroborated with European Prevalence of Infection in Intensive Care Study¹⁸.

Low prevalence of HAI in our study might be influenced by the significant number of chronic patients being treated in hospital wards such as psychiatry, dermatology and other lifestyle diseases and not exposed to other infectious patients. Second, many wards do not have AC and are dependent on traditional windows and fans for ventilation. These wards get more sunlight and fresh air as compared to wards with central AC/split AC which have recycled air and probably increased risk of HAI.

Single-patient rooms with independent window AC for acute care, rather than multiple-patients' room with recycled central AC, and more exposure to fresh air and sunlight for non-acute wards, may sound a retrograde step, but, as per the study, it appears to be a healthier option to reduce the risk to acquire HAI.

Our study had several limitations. First, it was performed in only one of the hospital. The one-time prevalence study nature might have influenced the prevalence rate and not depict the true rate as also the inability to determine the causal factors. For calculating patient-days, the cut-off was taken as the date of survey and not the date of discharge. However, compared to time-consuming and costly resource intensive incidence studies, repeated prevalence surveys are practical and efficient method of measuring trends over time. Such surveys can be used to provide data on infected and non-infected patients and assess the impact of infection prevention and control programmes on HAI³².

In conclusion our study revealed that HAI prevalence was 5.6 per cent in the first round and it went down up to 1.6 per cent in the fourth round. Conscious effort needs to be taken by all concerned to reduce the duration of hospitalization stay, to the minimum. Use of devices such as urinary catheter and peripheral/central iv lines may be minimized. If these have to be used, these should be discontinued at the earliest. Role of type of AC and ventilation in effecting risk of HAI needs more study.

Conflicts of Interest:None.

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